

COVID-19 Bibliometrics 18th – 24th January 2021

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A. Medicine and Health

January 22, 2021 (The Lancet Resp. Med.)

Effect of anakinra versus usual care in adults in hospital with COVID-19 and mild-to-moderate pneumonia (CORIMUNO-ANA-1): a randomised controlled trial

The CORIMUNO-19 Collaborative Group

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600\(20\)30556-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600(20)30556-7)

In this French multicentre, open-label, Bayesian randomised clinical trial (CORIMUNO-ANA-1), the authors aimed to determine whether anakinra, a recombinant human IL-1 receptor antagonist, could improve outcomes in patients in hospital with mild-to-moderate COVID-19 pneumonia.

January 21, 2021 (JAMA)

Effect of Bamlanivimab as Monotherapy or in Combination With Etesevimab on Viral Load in Patients With Mild to Moderate COVID-19: A Randomized Clinical Trial

Robert L. Gottlieb, Ajay Nirula, Peter Chen et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2021.0202>

This randomized clinical trial compares the effects of 3 doses of bamlanivimab monotherapy (700 vs 2800 vs 7000 mg) vs combination bamlanivimab and etesevimab vs placebo on change in day 11 severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 viral load in patients with mild to moderate coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19).

January 21, 2020 (JAMA Ophthal.)

Presence of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in the Cornea of Viremic Patients With COVID-19

Maria Casagrande, Antonia Fitzek, Martin S. Spitzer et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaophthalmol.2020.6339>

In this case series carried out in a tertiary care facility, SARS-CoV-2 genomic RNA was detected in the cornea of 6 of 11 eyes of patients with viraemic coronavirus disease 2019. Although infectivity or the presence of viral structural proteins could not be confirmed in any eye, this report demonstrates the presence of viral genomic and subgenomic RNA of SARS-CoV-2 in the human cornea.

January 19, 2021 (PNAS)

In silico dynamics of COVID-19 phenotypes for optimizing clinical management

Chrysovalantis Voutouri, Mohammad Reza Nikmaneshi, C. Corey Hardin et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2021642118>

The SARS-CoV2 virus can result in asymptomatic disease right up to severe disease. There are many factors – both viral and host that can influence this. To better understand clinical heterogeneity and optimal treatment, the authors developed a comprehensive mathematical model incorporating elements of the innate and adaptive immune responses, the renin–angiotensin system (which the virus exploits for cellular entry), rates of viral replication, inflammatory cytokines, and the coagulation cascade. They describe their model in this paper.

January 19, 2021 (JAMA)

Readmission and Death after Initial Hospital Discharge among Patients With COVID-19 in a Large Multihospital System

John P. Donnelly, Xiao Qing Wang, Theodore J. Iwashyna et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.21465>

Although more patients are surviving severe COVID-19, there are limited data on outcomes after initial hospitalization. This study describes reasons for readmission, the use of ICU interventions during readmission, and proportions of death after initial hospital discharge of COVID-19 patients from US Veterans Affairs (VA) hospitals in March-June 2020.

B. Science and Engineering

January 29, 2021 (Annual Reviews in Control)

The Ockham's razor applied to COVID-19 model fitting French data

Mirko Fiacchini & Mazen Alamir.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arcontrol.2021.01.002>

This paper presents a data-based model for fitting the pandemic evolution in France. The time series on the 13 regions of France has been considered for fitting and validating the model. A simple, two-dimensional model with only two parameters demonstrated to be able to reproduce the time series concerning the number of daily death, the hospitalizations, intensive care and emergency accesses, and the daily number of positive tests. These results might contribute to stimulating a debate on the suitability of much more complex models for reproducing and forecasting the pandemic evolution.

January 28, 2021 (Infection, Genetics and Evolution)

Machine learning predictive model for severe COVID-19

Jianhong Kang, Ting Chen, Honghe Luo et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2021.104737>

Kang et al developed the predictive model for severe patients of COVID-19 based on the clinical data from the Tumor Center of Union Hospital affiliated with Tongji Medical College, China. They processed the results in the 5 steps. In feature selection, ALB showed a strong negative correlation ($r=0.771$, $P < 0.001$) whereas GLB ($r=0.661$, $P < 0.001$) and BUN ($r=0.714$, $P < 0.001$) showed a strong positive correlation with severity of COVID-19. TensorFlow was then applied to develop a neural network model. According to them, the model achieved good prediction performance, with an area under the curve value of 0.95.

January 14, 2021 (Chaos, Solitons & Fractals)

A SIR-type model describing the successive waves of COVID-19

Gustavo A. Munoz-Fernandez, Jesus M. Seoane, Juan B. Seoane-Sepulveda.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2021.110682>

The authors show that the official data released by several countries (Italy, Spain and The USA) regarding the expansion of COVID-19 are compatible with a non-autonomous SIR type model with vital dynamics and non-constant population, calibrated according to exponentially decaying infection and death rates. They then construct a model whose outcomes for most relevant parameters, such as the number of active cases, cumulative deaths, daily new deaths and daily new cases fit available real data about the first and successive waves of COVID-19.

January 12, 2021 (Journal of Infection and Public Health)

Modelization of Covid-19 Pandemic Spreading: A Machine Learning Forecasting with Relaxation Scenarios of Countermeasures

Moulay A. Lmater, Mohamed Eddabbah, Tariq Elmoussaoui et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiph.2021.01.004>

The researchers performed a mathematical model according to a SIDR model for infectious diseases. Epidemiological data from Belgium, Morocco, Netherlands and Russia, are used to validate this model. They validated a new way of data aggregation, modelling and interpretation to predict the spread of Covid-19, evaluate the efficiency of countermeasures and suggest potential scenarios.

C. Social Sciences, Humanity and Public Policy

January 28, 2021 (Personality and Individual Differences)

Public attention about COVID-19 on social media: An investigation based on data mining and text analysis

Keke Hou, Tingting Hou & Lili Cai.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2021.110701>

This article examines social media responses to the pandemic and its management in China. A careful analysis provides a few surprising insights. A more careful approach to editing the paper would have improved its accessibility. Whether the findings are translatable to other countries' experience is for the reader to determine.

January 21, 2021 (Nature Human Behavior)

Increase in suicide following an initial decline during the COVID-19 pandemic in Japan

Takanao Tanaka & Shohei Okamoto.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-020-01042-z>

This paper considers whether the pandemic has harmed psychological health and exacerbated suicide risk. Based on month-level records of suicides covering the entire Japanese population in 1,848 administrative units, it was found that monthly suicide rates declined by 14% during the first 5 months of the pandemic (February to June 2020). By contrast, monthly suicide rates increased by 16% during the second wave (July to October 2020), with a larger increase among females (37%) and children and adolescents (49%). The authors point to several complex reasons, including the government's generous subsidies, reduced working hours and school closures during the first wave. Effective suicide prevention—particularly among vulnerable populations—should be an important public health consideration in responding to the pandemic.

January 21, 2021 (Structural Change and Economic Dynamics)

Predicting the spread of COVID-19 in Italy using machine learning: Do socio-economic factors matter?

Francesco Bloise & Massimiliano Tancioni.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.strueco.2021.01.001>

The paper investigates the provincial/ geographic variability of COVID-19 cases registered in Italy. The authors apply machine learning to isolate, among 77 potential predictors, those that minimize the out-of-sample prediction error. The results initially highlight the dominance of factors related to the intensity and interactions of economic activities whereas in a second analysis the relevance of these variables is highly reduced, suggesting mitigation of the pandemic following the lockdown of the economy.

In considering cases at the onset of the “second wave”, the authors confirm that the geographic distribution of the epidemic is indeed associated with economic factors.

January 16, 2021 (International Review of Financial Analysis)

Economic resiliency and recovery, lessons from the financial crisis for the COVID-19 pandemic: A regional perspective from central and Eastern Europe
Josef C. Brada, Pawel Gajewski & Ali M. Kutan.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2021.101658>

In this paper, the authors simulate the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the ability of upper-middle-income countries to recover from a shock to employment caused by the incidence of COVID-19. Using recoverability equation estimates, they find that employment in no more than 31 of the 199 regions will have fully recovered in 2 years following the onset of recovery from the crisis. The implications of the findings for policy are discussed.